

ORNAMENTAL PLANTS USED FOR FLOWER ARRANGEMENTS

Khakberdiyev Alikhuja Muratovich

Teacher, Samarkand State Architectural and Civil-Engineering Institute, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Abstract. *Through this article, future landscape designers will get acquainted with one, two and perennial flowers for flowerbeds from small floral arrangements. Information is given on what area and soil to plant flowers for flower beds, the correct choice of flowers depending on their flowering sequence, parameters (low, medium and high).*

Keywords: *Decorative plants, flowers, annuals, biennials, perennials, low-growing plants, medium-sized plants, tall plants*

Introduction

Each landscape designer chooses a set of flowers individually when designing small floral arrangements for any area. The decision-making process is primarily influenced by the taste of the beauty lover.

For every florist, experience plays an important role in growing this or that flower. In the process of planting flowers, due to factors such as improper location of the area, improperly selected soil, making mistakes in their cultivation can not achieve the desired result.

In small flower gardens, annual, biennial and perennial plants are selected for the selection and planting of flowers. Some people use annual flowers as a floral composition because they get tired of the monotony quickly. However, there are varieties of biennials and perennials that people never get bored of enjoying their beauty.

The purpose of this article is to study the morphological and biological characteristics of annual, biennial and perennial flowers and to introduce the types of flowers that can be used in the composition of a small flower bed.

The task is:

Collection of material on the composition of the flower bed and the annual, biennial and perennial plants used in it;

Targeted use of special literature and magazines, normative documents, analog drawings and projects, the Internet on the topic of the assignment; Systematic approach to the task, the tasks to be performed independently;

to complete the work on the basis of compositional tools, geometric and harmonic laws;

to develop skills and apply professional skills to apply the acquired knowledge and skills in life.

Annual flowering plants for flowerbed composition. It is hard to imagine most of the landscape architecture objects without flower beds. Flower beds are divided into several types, including flowerbeds, mixborders, rabatkas, modular flower beds, and more. The plants used for such flower beds are divided into annual, biennial and perennial.

It is convenient to plant in flower gardens from simple and bright annual plants, because with such plants can decorate flower arrangements every year at will. Annuals can be planted from seed or as seedlings.

By planting flowers that bloom at different heights and at different times in the flowerbed, it is possible to create a beautiful flower garden that blooms all summer long.

Low-growing annuals: These plants can be planted at the edges of flower beds, around trees, shrubs and perennials, to create curbs in sidewalks. Spaces in the flower bed based on perennial flowers can be filled with low annuals.

Among landscape experts, the most popular and popular flowers from low-growing plants are:

Velvet is distinguished by its orange-brown flowers throughout the summer. The height of this flower reaches a height of 20 cm. Velvet blooms not only in the sun but also in the semi-shade for a long time.

Lobelia is a low, spreading shrub, a small flowering plant in dark red (white), white, blue or purple. This flower loves moist soil and sunny places. The plant looks great when used in flower beds, curbs and hanging vases.

Iberis blooms mainly in white. It grows up to 30 cm in height, prefers soft local soils and can grow in partial shade. This plant can be planted in rabatka, flower beds and aisles.

Petunia is a favorite plant and comes in a variety of colors, such as the color of the rainbow. Petunias bloom from the first months of summer until the cold weather. She loves the heat and the sun. It is best to buy this plant as a seedling or as a flowering plant.

Medium-sized annual plants for flowerbed composition: Two-horned *Mattiola* grows to a height of 50 cm and blooms all summer long. The plant is famous for its beautiful flowers, which begin to emit a divine scent after sunset.

Cosmos is one of the most difficult-to-find plants. This flower grows up to 80 cm in height and the flowers are dark red, pink or white. It is a fragile plant with delicate leaves and grows well in partial shade.

Dimorphoteka flowers are well suited for compositions of annuals as well as perennials. This flower should be planted in sunny, open ground. Any floral composition made of *dimorphoteka* gives the atmosphere a festive mood.

Zinnia blooms in white, pink, purple, yellow or red throughout the summer until frost. This flower loves light and loves fertile soil. In most cases, the plant is planted in groups on flower beds and lawns.

Salvia is a bear plant that grows up to 30 cm in height and is compatible with many plants in the flower garden.

Annual tall plants for flowerbed composition: Tall plants in groups give good results in the flower bed. These little evergreens are super-easy to grow and will look good with almost no care.

Among the tall flowering annuals are:

Amaranth is a plant that has 30 different appearances. In late summer, it blooms in red, in the form of candles, grows up to 150 cm in height, and the leaves of some species are also reddish.

Malva flowers grow up to 130 cm in height. This bear plant blooms all summer long with beautiful flowers. Its large flowers are reminiscent of a bell. *Malva* is planted in the form of seedlings in May.

Kleshivina (castor oil) or the tree of paradise is an exotic plant that is absolutely barren. It is famous for its large leaves that resemble the leaves of a palm tree. In a short time, the cliché grows to a height of 150 cm.

Datura or durman- the plant blooms with white, blue, red and yellow flowers resembling bells. Grows up to 1 meter tall in fertile soil. *Datura* blooms all summer long until frost. Annual bear (non-selective) flowers that turn from a seed into a beautiful flower in one season tend to be noticeable. With proper care of such flowers, it is possible to prolong the flowering period and spread the sea of people with its bright colors, giving a beautiful view of the environment.

Two year old flowers for flowerbed composition. This type of flowering plant is propagated from seed and transplanted after it has grown. An important aspect of biennial plants is that they do not bloom from the first year.

Bell - The plant can grow up to 80 cm in height. The flowers can be fluffy or simple. Available in Pink, White, Blue, or Purple.

The plant likes sunny places, but does not like windy places. They are planted at a depth of 0.5 cm in May-June. By the end of summer, they are transplanted to a permanent place according to the scheme 30x40 cm. Flowers appear only in 2 years.

Three different colored purple. Another name is *Viola Vitrokka*. Plant height - no more than 30 cm. The color of the flowers can be single or multi-colored (up to 2-3 colors). Seedlings are planted in March (probably February). The plant is dormant and blooms throughout the summer when grown in a sunny area.

Turkish clove is a beautiful plant that grows up to 60 cm in height. Looks great in the flowerbed. On the dark green stems are formed dense caps of inflorescences of different colors. The plant is grown from seed and transplanted in the second year. It grows well in both sun and partial shade.

Perennial flowers for flowerbed composition. Although many landscape experts do not bloom all summer long, they are resistant to the cold weather of winter, easy to care for and maintain, can be propagated in parts, and through them give a modern look to small flower beds prefer perennials that give.

Small flower beds made of perennials should be chosen not only on the color of flowers, but also on the parameters of the plants. For example, planting tall, bright, and large-flowered perennials in the center of the flowerbed; against the background of tall plants should be planted perennials of medium height; it is advisable to fill the edges and cavities of the flower bed with low-growing plants.

Low-growing perennials. The main difference of low-growing flowers is that they can be axed not only to the edges of small flower beds, but also to create patterns or drawings on small ponds, rocky cliffs or lawns.

Dwarf aster is one of the most popular plants in gardens. Its flowers come in many colors and bloom until July, when the weather is cold. *Astra* prefers regular watering and partial shade.

Balsam - with its bright flowers decorates flower beds and curbs until the cold weather. This plant also grows well in the shade and in any soil.

Alissumis a yellow and blue flowering plant with a collection of flowers that blooms until late autumn. This flower can be planted in flower beds and on rocky cliffs. The plant prefers dry, fertilized soil and requires regular pruning of dried branches.

Aquilegia loves moist soil, so it is recommended to plant it near water bodies. Does not require large amounts of fertilizer.

Tall perennials. *Peony* is a thick shrub that grows quickly and blooms in different colors. Requires regular watering, timely feeding, pruning of dried branches. Peonies amaze people not only with their beauty but also with their wonderful aroma.

Astilbais a fluffy flower of different colors that grows even in the shade. It is one of the longest flowering perennials (up to ten weeks). *Astilbes* grow in different sizes depending on the navigation. The plant loves regular watering and feeding.

Gladiolus is an onion-like perennial plant that blooms from July to September. Some varieties of plants bloom within 70 days after transplanting. Because *gladiolus* comes in a variety of colors, it can be used to create unusual compositions for flower beds. It is recommended to transfer this flower to partial shade.

Chamomile is a plant that will not leave indifferent people who love flowers. With proper care, they bloom for a long time and grow fast. It is recommended to plant chamomile in sunny areas, as it does not grow well in the shade.

Delphinium is the king of blue flowering plants. Today there are varieties of this flower that bloom in pink, yellow and orange. The plant blooms in June and July, requires no care and tolerates cold winter weather well. Properly selected flowers for the flowerbed will make it beautiful and bright, and will bloom from spring to the cold days of winter. A flower lover who knows the types and varieties of flowers well can create an unusual and beautiful flower garden.

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